

DEVELOPMENT OF THE CLUSTER OF ART EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN.

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ABSTRACT

The article extensively highlights the need to create a cluster of art education in Uzbekistan and the factors that make up the cluster of art education, the functions of which have been extensively studied. Analytical methods and proposals for the formation and justification of the activity of the cluster of art education in the republic are highlighted.

Introduction. It is recognized by the world's leading art experts that our country maintains the uniqueness of national artistic traditions as a hotbed of ancient civilisation, which has made a great contribution to the development of world art and culture with its rich artistic heritage. The cluster of artistic education, which includes the development of art and applied art, Performing Arts, Museum Business, Design, Creative Industries, the preservation of cultural heritage, the reproduction of highly qualified young personnel in the field of culture and art, will become a great basis for the full implementation of not only the "growth point" of the cultural and social development of Uzbekistan,

The reforms carried out in the education system of the republic have opened up wide opportunities for organizing the content of education on the basis of universal human resources and historical and cultural traditions of our people. As a result, a new generation of educational standards, training programs, textbooks was created. At the moment they are being improved, modernization is in kilinmok. The idea of a perfect person is a noble idea that has both national and Universal leprosy, embodies the highest spiritual and physical perfection inherent in human beings, which encourages him to good hamisha [1].

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY.

The development of national traditions of cultural heritage and high artistry, its use, the introduction of methods of creative practice, work with natural material teach people, especially young people, diligence, endurance, perseverance, philosophical, psychological, aspects of Fine Art in higher educational institutions in maksadi to educate students-youth in political-ideological and aesthetic permission, to perceive beauty, to study works of fine art, to, plays an important role in the formation of skills and WorldView [3].

Republic Of Uzbekistan 2022 — In the development strategy of the New Uzbekistan aimed at development during 2026 years: development of fine and Applied Arts and design directions, raising the artistic and aesthetic taste of the population, wide promotion of exemplary life and creativity of famous people's artists and masters of Applied Art of Uzbekistan, perpetuating their memory, popularizing the fine and Applied Art of Uzbekistan at the international level. After all, the artistic and cultural way of life of the people, its place in the future within the peoples of the world, is the reason for the widespread promotion of the cultural and spiritual norm of the Uzbek people [1].

Improving the activities of cultural centers and improving the quality of cultural services for the population, establishing new cultural objects in the regions and ensuring their effective functioning, introducing activities aimed at popularizing national culture at the international level, carrying out complex activities related to the preservation, restoration and conservation of cultural heritage sites located in the territory of the Republic, and, counted from the most leading tasks.

Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers on specialized art and culture schools and boarding schools in the system of the Ministry of culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 9, 2019 [2] was approved, which on the basis of the decision was the first link of the art education cluster-schools of Arts and their improvement.

Practical experiments were carried out in the leading state of the world on the organization of art education clusters and the effective organization of their activities, from foreign researchers: Ch. Lendri [10], R. Fluoride [11] and Dj. Paina [12], DC. Scientists such as Gilmora [13] can be included. Among the practitioners in the field of art clusters in Russia; E. Zoev [6], D. E. Milkov [7], M. B. Gnedovsky [8], E. V. An example is Zelensova [9] and other domestic researchers.

The cluster sector is developing widely in the Republic of Uzbekistan. In this regard, agricultural, medical, textile, waste processing, agricultural network clusters carry out extensive practical activities. Large-scale innovative activities in the field of education of our country are being carried out in the field of Education. In this regard, we need to describe the "Chirchik" model of the innovation cluster of pedagogical education. The organization of an educational cluster is defined as the main task of ensuring the effective functioning of each of its links. G'as the founders of the education cluster. I. Mukhamedov, O. Khadjamkulov, Sh. I. Batarova, S. Our scientists, such as Toshtemirova, are widely implementing educational cluster activities with their research.

Cluster mechanisms operating in various sectors of the economy, agriculture and national economy in our country also indicate the need for implementation in the educational system. In this regard, a cluster of advanced innovative pedagogical education in the field of education, identifying the existing shortcomings in each of the sections of the educational system of Uzbekistan, combining them under a common goal, is determined to operate in a special interest for each network. From this, the organization of art education at the cluster level is considered appropriate even in the field of art education.

For the formation of a cluster of pedagogical education, a number of important conditions are required:

- establishing mutual cooperation between educational institutions using the competitive advantages of the territory;

- identification of leaders who determine long-term innovations and other strategies of the entire system;
- establishment of scientific organizations that make it possible to improve the level of qualifications of employees of an educational institution that ensures internal and external competitiveness;
- atmosphere of trust and creativity;
- it is possible to include such as the presence of private interest of educational institutions in one area, which comes from a common goal.

The importance of the pedagogical education cluster by area is seen in:

- in the economic sphere: contributes to the formation of a market for effective educational services;
- in the social sphere:
 - promotes the employment of graduates of pedagogical educational institutions; in the field of marketing:
 - innovation popularizes educational technologies, new opportunities in educational and educational work of educational institutions;
 - in the legal field: provides an opportunity to establish mutual cooperation within the framework of the cluster, as well as to create regulatory framework related to the transition to new forms of management of educational institutions;
 - in the field of pedagogy: continuing education makes it possible to jointly design the training of pedagogical personnel in the system [4].

The purpose of the activities of specialized schools and boarding schools is to educate students in the specialty subjects in a deep and profession-oriented manner, to ensure their intellectual development and spiritual development, and to educate them in a high patriotic spirit. In this regard, from the mutual harmony of artistic creativity and the educational system, a new creative direction comes – art education, and this is the sphere that has gone through several stages in its history. In the educational system, the art-learning cluster is an innovation chain based mainly on horizontal links within the chain "science - creativity - means of teaching, interaction and self-study in business" [5].

Artistic art it is considered an area of \ u200b \ u200bcarciety designed to cover all areas of life, not being a closed system. One of the main tasks of artistic art is to influence the spiritual and cultural development of a person and the development of territories under its influence. Today, the organization of a modern conceptual exhibition requires its own solutions, which, indicating the need for artistic education, requires a specific architectural space, that is, the further development of Modern Art (Art cluster). The organization of such art education clusters, in turn, provides conditions for improving the skills of creative workers in the field of Culture and art, attracting highly qualified employees to Uzbekistan, creating an area of inter-sectoral cooperation and cultural exchange between regions, improving the skills of creative workers in the field of culture and art, cultural services and products provided to the population,

DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS.

The growth of the sphere of creative and artistic art leads to the main changes in economic systems: the formation of an economy of knowledge - the formation of an art market and the

establishment of a mechanism for its proper functioning, the growth of the service sector and the strengthening of the participation of the subjects of the cluster of artistic education in On the basis of the introduction of art-marketing concepts of a modern nature into art education, the main task is to create a wide circular direction of movement of works, which is a product of art education.

Specialized schools and boarding schools are state educational institutions that provide for the professional orientation of students in specialty subjects and their targeted training so that they can continue their further education in higher educational institutions or engage in labor activities, carry out the educational process in accordance with the requirements of state educational standards, state educational requirements, educational plans and educational programs,

The artistic-educational cluster is an innovative chain based mainly on horizontal links within the chain "science - creativity - means of teaching, mutual learning and self-study in business" system. A clustered approach to art education helps to better understand the relationship between the basic learning processes of art and art education [14].

In the formation of the art education cluster, we are talking about the international M. We preferred to use three stages of the cluster formation methodology developed by Porter:

- 1) creation of the structure of the art cluster: separation of the core of the art education cluster, establishing educational progress based on the subject and direction with additional horizontal connections (interaction with government, science, public organizations); Organization of cluster communications in the artistic direction in the horizontal and vertical direction;
- 2) separation of groups of subjects (organizations, institutions) that provide special infrastructure-forming skills, technologies within the framework of the cluster of artistic education;
- 3) identification of government and other legislative structures in influencing the behavior of cluster participants (according to the "three spirals" Model (government-scientific and educational center-business)).

One of the goals of the cluster principle is the organization of art schools on a cluster basis and the training of specialists in the field of art education in them, the provision of mature specialists in the field of practical, visual and design effective activities in each of the sections of the industry. According to the professions chosen by students in the field of art and culture:

- Organization of quality training in accordance with the requirements of the state educational standard, which is deepened in the disciplines of the specialty and is focused on the profession;
- implementation of specialized educational programs within the framework of state educational requirements, which ensure a high level of quality knowledge and professional training so that in the future he can continue his studies at a higher educational institution or engage in labor activity in accordance with his chosen profession and specialty;
- provision of highly qualified personnel in the field of art and culture, implementation of international cooperation on educational issues in accordance with the legislation; satisfaction of the need of young people for consistent intellectual, cultural and spiritual and moral perfection, their upbringing in the spirit of devotion to the native land, high civic, human qualities, National ideas, spiritual-historical, universal values of their

The content of the art education cluster educational direction is as follows:

development of mechanisms for identifying, classifying and eliminating existing problems in artistic education;

improving the educational and methodological potential of literary education;

management and control of the quality of literature lessons;

development of simple and optimal mechanisms for determining the educational and methodological effectiveness of literature lessons and their implementation in the practice of literary education;

establishment of activities of inter-educational teacher-student system on literary education.

The educational direction of the literary education cluster is aimed at ensuring the integration of literary education in the framework of cooperation in the means of organizing, managing, improving the quality of education, improving educational methodological work in this regard. The cluster cooperation model is formed from the integration of types of education in a holistic system and around a common goal as a rational solution to ensuring integration.

The cluster is a system in which the integration of the components that make it up ensures that each subject works more efficiently and does not lead to exceptional distortions. The cluster is caused not by the mechanical fusion of a number of educational and scientific and production entities into a specific association, but by their close interaction and interdependence. The term cluster has come into our country from agricultural industry specialists, and various industry and network clusters are currently operating.

A special role of the art cluster in connection with the development of Modern Art is played by the fact that cities, as well as the recovery of territories freed from production, form art clusters that grow special systemic and continuous artistic - art products in cities, small and medium - sized creative enterprises with regions with cheap labor, and they are formed on the basis.

Art clusters are a separate space in which several enterprises, firms, workshops, offices are united in one common space and the industrial sector engaged in artistic creation is assembled. The main feature of art clusters is the creation of an atmosphere of creativity and business that promotes the creation and production of products of widespread artistic creation [15].

Educational clusters are also theoretically an analogue of production clusters. Practical processes related to their establishment Kil are similar to ham. Studying the experience associated with the use of such an approach to the educational system, the analysis of literature shows that the following is takozo:

- integration of production and educational programs;
- cluster approach to education integration of production and educational programs to demonstrate in the structure as a means of supporting innovation (science-education - development;
- to become an effective way to organize innovative activities of the formation of Personnel potential for the future economy;
- Organization of kayta on the principle of continuity of the educational system with various educational institutions (kindergarten, school, Lyceum, College, University).

The main center of the art education cluster is the Academy of Arts of Uzbekistan, around which the subjects of the cluster begin to unite.

1-picture. Structure of the artistic education cluster of Uzbekistan.

Improving the activities of cultural centers and improving the quality of cultural services for the population, establishing new cultural objects in the regions and ensuring their effective functioning, introducing activities aimed at popularizing national culture at the international level, carrying out complex activities related to the preservation, restoration and conservation of cultural heritage sites located in the territory of the Republic, and, counted from the most leading tasks.

Before the broad coverage of artistic educational creativity, the professional qualifications of the creative person and his

Creativity is a higher level of consciousness, a higher and more complex form of activity, which is inherent in a person. Creativity is a miracle that is born as a result of the mobilization of all mental processes of a person, all knowledge, skills, all life experience, moral, physical strength, as an original and historical-ijt Imo, unique qualitative innovation. The result of creativity in art, including Fine Art, will be the creation of a work of art [7].

When the professionogram of creative persons engaged in artistic creation is illuminated, it is noticeable that there are several types of professional and cognitive competencies that must be mastered by them. In the process of their analysis, a creative person engaged in artistic creation: regardless of whether he is an expert in the field of Applied Art or design, be it fine arts, it is established that primary cognitive abilities prevail in them than representatives of other fields.[5] the cognitive competencies of a creative person are as follows::

1. Motivation and desire
2. Freedom and independence
3. Artistic perception
4. Creative imagination

5. Imagination and image

6. Sensitivity and imagery
7. Creative and design thinking
8. Estetek worldview-nature observation
9. Drawing a draft, Execution of Etudes
10. Thinking about what is seen
11. Work on composite sketches
12. "Inner" intuition and intuition[6]
13. Hotira and contemplation
14. Emotion and mobility
15. Agility and perseverance
16. Patience

17. Features such as self-control form the basis of the professionogram of a creative person. To become a mature specialist in the industry, the ability plays an important role in the creator. And abilities are formed regularly, the basis of which is tireless work and creativity. For specialists in the artistic field, knowledge is a vital material, a deep and comprehensive study of life, without which a work of art cannot be created. Knowledge of life in the pictorial or applied field affects the feelings of the firstborn, creator, and as a result, an image is formed.

Without first studying logical and hissy cognition with organic coherence, figurative thinking cannot be developed, without which, in turn, artistic images cannot be created either. The creator of the artistic sphere should be a well-versed, educated and educated person in all aspects of life. In addition, he must transfer his knowledge through his senses and reflect in a generalized form in the form of an artistic image[7]

In a creative person, cognitive abilities are formed as a result of the above interrelated processes. In such creativity, originality and vivid imagination cause them to differ sharply from other representatives of the industry. Cognitive abilities in a creative person are constantly perfected as a result of qualifications and experience. Each of the disciplines in the artistic direction has some similar and unique requirements. It will be possible to study the similarities and differences of labor - actions in the field of artistic creativity. Cognitive needs and development are reflections, interpretations and concepts in all artistic Sciences and are widely used in all areas of art.

A specialist in the field of artistic education should find a unanimity between methods that require and develop complex thinking in the study of various artistic forms, develop complex art programs, and understand the essence of thinking in artistic teaching. Research in the field of art science should take into account not only the specific form of art being studied, but also the peculiarities of the specific artistic experience that the student faces. (competencies that must be developed based on their orientation)

Designer creating in the direction of art education:L.A.According to Klaykova's definition, "it requires the formation of artistic-aesthetic competence, and it regulates the system of internal means of regulating the aesthetic direction based on competence, direct artistic-aesthetic knowledge, skills and experiences, and carries out artistic - aesthetic actions"[8]. In them, the development of a specific aesthetic and artistic taste, extroversion, the ability to figuratively express processes and phenomena; differs from other directions of art in the presence of a sense of harmony in the creation of a work of art.

The influence of artistic activity on the development of the personality of creative people and students contributing to the development of society is also important. With the help of artistic education, even young students form knowledge that is richer and more personally significant than required.

Artistic art has long been considered a high product of cognitive activity, which has been valued for a long time as the highest form of person's perception of the beauty of nature.[1] it should be noted that the cognitive knowledge of students studying in the field of artistic education in the process of engaging in artistic creation and pedagogical – psychological phenomena in educational and educational processes in creating the result of the product of creativity emphasize the need for a broad study of the activities of the creative person. [3]

In artistic education, the demand for systematicity and sequence in ensuring continuity and continuity of the field of fine and applied art and design is primarily aimed at maintaining the continuity of teaching. That is why teaching should be seen as a logically connected system in terms of content, purpose, methods, means at all stages of a continuing education system. This in turn ensures the promising development of the educational personality. It is considered the most important point in the system of continuing education in the field of fine and Applied Art in art education, as well as in ensuring continuity and continuity in the field of design. Therefore, it is extremely important to ensure continuity at the points of transition from one type of training mentioned above to another type of Education[3].

The art market is considered an excellent market in the economy. It represents the socio-economic and cultural-historical system of commodity circulation of works of art. In the art market, as well as in any other market, production, distribution, consumption and redistribution are carried out. But the main difference between the art market and the rest is the circulation of cultural values in society. How and why people strive to produce and consume cultural values.

The classic definition of marketing is F. Formulated by Kotler [1]: "Art marketing is a type of human activity aimed at satisfying demands and needs through exchange." There is a need in the center of marketing. Chunoichi, the manufacturer does not spend either money or labor on a product that the market does not need. Needs can be very different, but in any case, their origin lies in the need, which has a certain form in accordance with the wishes of the consumer. "Spiritual need is nothing more than a certain state of consciousness and manifests itself as a conscious call of a person to spiritual creation, creation and consumption of spiritual values. The second is the embodiment of the mind and feelings of people" [2].

The consumption and replacement of a commodity – art object is not associated with the expression of money, but with its spiritual consumption, that is, it becomes known how the public perceived certain objects of art and whether they are ready for their full perception. Once a spiritual need arises, the next logical stage is the production of a product to satisfy that need. In the art market, the production of products must be related to different marketing concepts. The first concept, in accordance with their evolution, is called "production". The main thesis can be formulated as "I produce what I can" it should be noted that this concept does not apply to the art market.

The essence of the production of an art object is that the costs and costs of its production are catastrophically small compared to almost any products in other economic markets. In a simplified version for painting, you only need paints, cysts and brushes; to write a book, you

need pencils and pieces of paper. Accordingly, in the art market there can be catastrophically many "producers". And only one great, but invaluable skill is talent, which only creative people can create. Talents, abilities and skills - the basis of experience [3] is revealed with the acquisition of certain or outstanding natural abilities. Accordingly, the concept of production cannot be used by artists, since consumers see in works of art "what not every second person can do."

Commodity concept, in contrast to the concept of production, can be used in production in the art market. Indeed, the leading idea of the commodity concept is formulated as "the production of quality goods." In the market considered by the author, the quality of the product is its specificity, its assessment is possible. Artists go a long way from the very beginning of their work to the times when they are truly recognized. And this is the main direction that should be followed in the art market.

The socio-moral concept of marketing is the production of what the consumer needs, taking into account the basic requirements of society. The founders of Impressionism, such as Edouard Manet or Edgar Degas, were revolutionary artists who, thanks to a subtle analysis of the new demands of society, turned the entire world of painting in the late 19th century. And at the time of their success, the competition was not so strong, since most of the artists could not move away from the aforementioned academicism.

The result.

As a result of the analysis of the art education cluster, it was found that the development of artistic creativity includes several competencies, and they determine the relationship of the creative person with their peers among themselves, including peers, teachers and family, and can influence them.

The main influencing factors are the interaction of the subjects of the cluster during practical exercises in the field of art education, active exchange in production planning and the relationship to works of art officially ordered by the consumer. Artistic art can strengthen the subject relationship in schools, it is often necessary to provide many opportunities for cooperation, and ensuring the participation of students, teachers, creators of the artistic sphere and parents will greatly contribute to the significant development of continuing art education. The study of important forms of artistic art and the connections between them determines the need for research at the level of the art education cluster and requires study in further research. Many experts in this field believe that during the research of Art marketing tasks in art and culture, marketers in the field of art and culture should bring the products of artistic creation and its consumer to the people's platform, or rather, create optimal conditions. In Art marketing, the main link is aimed at a non-artistic product (non-profit link, the main one is reflected in the social aspect as the complete fulfillment of the task. The second task lies in the presence of sufficient access to the product of artistic creativity, which is aimed at the financial market.

The main product in the art of art, not the consumer. Since marketing is controlled by producers in the context of an industrial developed society, it is important to conclude that today the most important function of art is the product determined by artistic creators. As you know, the main advantage of an artistic product lies in its real originality. This is especially true when an artistic product is focused on socio-artistic in the role of re-consumer in carrying out creative activities, moving to meet artistic and aesthetic needs[6].

There is a clear law for this position — an artistic product forms the public. The artist, that is, the producer, creates a unique artistic product, and advanced consumers-as a rule, elite representatives try to buy it.

Management of the field of artistic art is considered a component of modern management and art studies, arising from the perception of art as a system that creates conditions for the cultural and creative process, and is intended as an activity aimed at coordinating people with the results of labor in the field of culture and art in order to increase the level of.

Many practical tasks were performed by Babkov on the development of the concept of marketing and Art art education, describing the cooperation of Art cluster and Art management as follows: "art art and culture is a business, large art education and large culture is a big business, and art education and culture is a business of the third millennium"[8].

A number of important conditions are required to form an art education cluster. In the generalization of the cluster of Art Management and art education, the cluster rule must find its practical result, that is, it must be carried out through the totality of goals and the totality of interests. There are several criteria in this, which are as follows:

- Establishing mutual cooperation between educational institutions using the competitive advantages of the territory in the organization of art clusters, practical actions of artistic creators;
- Art management and art clustering under a holistic system and identifying leaders defining long-term innovations and other strategies of the entire system;
- on the example of organizing and maintaining the activities of areducational institutions that ensure internal and external competitiveness, as well as scientific organizations that make it possible to increase the level of qualifications of creative employees of the educational institution (art master workshop at the Academy of Arts of Uzbekistan;
- Formation of an atmosphere of trust and creativity in the art cluster and its management[9] ;
- the inclusion of educational institutions in a single territory, such as the presence of private interest arising from a common goal, is considered the main criterion that ensures the development of the industry.

Development and development of the abilities of young creative people operating in the field of artistic education, creation of works of high level; development of advanced methods of reading the traditions of artistic education of young creative people following the traditions of "teacher-student" and introduction of creative creative workshops; selection of talented young artists working in the fields of Fine Arts (machine-tool, graphics, as a result of ensuring the inextricable supply of art education with Art Management, the following features develop:

- Organization of creative trips of young artists of the higher art course to foreign countries at the maximum level of familiarization with unique works, copying and exchange of experience in exhibitions and museums abroad;
- to promote the regular enrichment of the funds of the museums of our country with works of Fine Art with a high artistic trick; to rag the creators in every possible way and to expand the creative potential of talented youth, and to develop creative ties of chalcaro;
- it is envisaged to make good use of the creative opportunities of young specialists working in the fields of fine and applied art, create the necessary conditions for them, achieve a high degree of expression of national and universal tradition in works of Art, increase the artistic level of exhibitions held in our country.

To the point. The master workshop of painting is the most important in the development of skills and abilities, the systematic increase of creative skills and potential in foreign higher educational institutions, the organization of creative and practical exchange of experience, the training of personnel on the basis of joint educational programs in the fields with these educational institutions in order to further develop halkaro cooperation[7]

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